

UK Innovation in Immersive XR Technologies for screen, performance and digital entertainment: industry funding trends and insights (2006–2024)

A Foresight Lab Report

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Driven by the UK's leading Creative Industries experts, the [CoSTAR Foresight Lab](#) is researching the adoption, use and impact of new, emergent and convergent technologies in gaming, TV, film, performance and digital entertainment.

Our findings will inform research, development and innovation across the Creative Industries, including the R&D taking place through the convergent screen technologies and performance in real time (CoSTAR) programme, the UK R&D network for creative technology.

[CoSTAR](#) is a £75.6 million national R&D network of laboratories that are developing new technology to maintain the UK's world-leading position in gaming, TV, film, performance, and digital entertainment. Delivered by the UKRI Arts and Humanities Research Council, the programme is supporting new innovations and experiences that will enrich the UK's creative industries, economy, and culture. The network comprises the National Lab, the Realtime Lab, the Live Lab, the Screen Lab and the Foresight Lab. CoSTAR is funded through UK Research and Innovation's Infrastructure Fund, which supports the facilities, equipment and resources that are essential for researchers, businesses, and innovators to do groundbreaking work. You can find out more by visiting www.costarnetwork.co.uk.

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ABOUT THIS REPORT

This report surveys extended reality (XR) activity in the UK between 2006 and 2024, funded by bodies such as national arts councils, local councils, charities, and commercial entities (rather than UK Research and Innovation). We survey the landscape of XR activity from the perspectives of the technologies being used, the use cases for those technologies, and the organisations supporting this work. This report is a companion piece to the report '[UK Innovation in Immersive XR Technologies for screen, performance and digital entertainment: UKRI funding trends and insights \(2006–2024\)](#)' published by the CoSTAR Foresight Lab in May 2025. That previous report provided an overview of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) investment into XR technologies for screen, performance and digital entertainment until the close of 2024. Our new analysis allows a comparison of the work funded by UKRI with that funded by other bodies as well as commercial ventures. Together, these reports provide a baseline from which to track key trends in XR activity before the formation of the [CoSTAR Network](#).

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

OVERVIEW OF XR PROJECTS

- Between 2006 and 2024, we located 380 XR projects that took place in the UK in addition to those funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), with a marked increase from 2015 onwards. We found that the most mentioned technologies were augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR), accounting for 171 projects and 137 projects, respectively. The XR projects were distributed around the whole of the UK with concentrations in London, Cardiff, Bristol, Central Scotland, and the Midlands and North of England. Scotland had a proportionally higher number of XR projects relative to its population, England lower, and Northern Ireland and Wales an expected number of projects. London was the location of 58 of the 305 projects with location data, so the number of projects in London was slightly higher than expected relative to its population.

XR FUNDING LANDSCAPE BEYOND UKRI

- The most frequent type of funder was commercial entities, followed by community development, Business Improvement Districts or Local Enterprise Partnerships, local authorities, and arts organisations, venues or events. The most frequent individual funders were National Lottery Heritage Fund, Wellcome Trust, and Arts Council England. Funding awards over £1m were awarded to 10 projects between 2016 and 2023, mostly for the development of large-scale heritage and nature attractions.

TECHNOLOGIES: AR, VR, XR

- The most frequent use cases for AR were apps and trails, often at sites of historical interest and accessed using a smartphone app. The most frequent use cases for VR were in exhibitions, experiences, games, and for performances accessed using a VR headset. Other use cases of the remaining technologies extended to films, games, installations and performances, although there are many projects that defy easy categorisation.

VIRTUAL PRODUCTION

- We located 41 virtual production (VP) studios that were active in the UK in 2025 and had not received a direct UKRI funding award, all of which were founded in 2021 or later. 36 of the VP studios in the UK are commercial entities and the remaining 5 are based in academic institutions, indicating that VP is of strategic infrastructural importance to higher education, and worthy of its own investment.

TECH ADOPTION

- From the data we collected, it can be seen that early adopters of XR technologies employed a wide variety of use cases. Although there was no one clear early adopter in terms of sectors or funders, AR is the most popular XR technology employed by the projects (45% of the projects in this report) and its use is increasing. The adoption and increased use of XR technologies contributes to our understanding of innovation in the creative industries.

COMPARISON WITH UKRI FUNDED XR ACTIVITY

- We compared the 380 XR projects detailed in this report with the 529 projects funded by UKRI during that same period. UKRI started funding VP related research projects in Higher Education in 2014, and commercial VP studios began to be established in the UK in 2021. With many of these, the current provision of UK VP studios, technologies and skills can be traced back to early intervention and support from UKRI.

This all points to a vibrant XR sector in the UK attracting a range of public and private funding and extending to academic, commercial and public activities, with much overlap between the technologies, their use cases, and the organisations creating and using them.

This report expands upon existing mapping of extended reality (XR) activity in the UK to provide a benchmark for the state of play of investment in XR technologies at the close of 2024, against which the future effects of CoSTAR Network activities can be compared. This report provides an overview of XR activity in the UK by collating and analysing a dataset of projects funded by national arts councils, local councils, charities, and commercial entities. It is a companion piece to our previous report, '[UK Innovation in Immersive XR Technologies for screen, performance and digital entertainment: UKRI funding trends and insights \(2006–2024\)](#)', which was published in May 2025, focussing exclusively on investment by [UK Research and Innovation](#) (UKRI).

Technologies

XR encompasses a range of different technologies and associated use cases which require definition in terms of the environments they create

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INTRODUCTION

and how those environments relate to the physical world around us.

Extended reality (XR) is an umbrella term for augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies, and the descriptions of some projects only use the term XR without specifying further which modalities they are developing and using. AR has been described as “open and partially immersive environments that allow digital objects to be overlaid onto the physical world” (Immerse UK & Digital Catapult, 2019, p. 6), for example, using a smartphone app to look through the phone’s camera and see images or information overlaid on the camera images. VR has been described as “closed and fully immersive three-dimensional environments” (Immerse UK & Digital Catapult, 2019, p. 6), for example, 360-degree virtual environments viewable through a VR headset. MR has been described as “blending physical and virtual worlds to produce new environments and visualisations where physical and digital objects co-exist and interact in real time” (Immerse UK & Digital Catapult, 2019, p. 6), for example, a digital object viewable through a VR headset that can be manipulated and interacted with by the user. It has been suggested that this type of XR is at an earlier stage of development for public applications than AR and VR (Rokhsaritalemi et al., 2020); it is certainly less frequently mentioned by the projects we located.

Immersive is another umbrella term for similar technologies, although it is often used in other media production contexts to describe media that are designed to be more interactive or participatory, such as theatre productions that attempt to minimise the distance between audience and performer (Punchdrunk Enrichment, 2024). In defining the scope of this study, we have been careful to include only projects that are labelled immersive because they use AR, MR, VR or XR technologies. This report reflects further on the definitions and uses of the various XR technologies in later sections.

Virtual Production (VP) is a specific application of XR technologies to create digital environments that operate similarly to mixed reality in that it can combine physical and digital elements (Willment & Swords, 2023) and so has been included in this report.

This report focuses on XR, including VP, technologies implemented in similar contexts to those of the [CoSTAR Network](#). It therefore includes projects for the development of XR and VP technologies, and projects that use these technologies for gaming, TV, film, performance, and digital entertainment purposes, across traditional media and performance spaces as well as in heritage and tourist spaces.

Research Questions

We designed this report to provide data about the landscape of XR activity in the UK beyond that funded by UKRI by developing a set of research questions. The research questions were designed to establish a methodology for this kind of data work by determining what data is available, from where, and what questions they can be used to answer. We then interrogated the data to gain an overview of XR activity in the UK, the technologies involved, the sectors that are implementing these technologies and the organisations responsible for funding innovation in this space. This work was undertaken to provide a baseline from which to track XR activity before the establishment of the CoSTAR Network in 2024. We also sought to identify trends in XR activity to shape our future work in this area.

We expect this report will be useful for researchers, academics, industry bodies and creative organisations interested in the uptake of XR technologies in the UK and their future use.

This report asks, in a pre-CoSTAR UK landscape:

- What data is available about XR activity in the UK?
- What does the UK's XR landscape look like?
- What is the geographic distribution of XR projects?
- Which technologies are most frequently used?
- What are the most popular use cases for these technologies?
- Which sectors are involved in innovating use cases for these technologies?
- Which organisations (outside of UKRI) are funding the adoption of these technologies?
- What trends can we identify that might shape the future of XR and VP?
- How do these findings compare to UKRI-funded XR activity?

METHODS

In this report we survey the landscape of XR activity from the perspectives of the technologies being used, the use cases for those technologies, and the organisations supporting this work. While the details of all UKRI-funded projects since 2006 are publicly accessible via an online database, [Gateway to Research](#), there is no convenient comparable source of XR activity in the UK that is funded or supported by other resources not linked to UKRI.

We therefore developed a structured search strategy designed to locate as much relevant data as possible. As well as an exercise in mapping the landscape of XR activity in the UK, this report also locates and evaluates potential sources of data for this purpose. We located several sources of data, including lists of funded projects made available by [Arts Council England](#), [Arts Council NI](#), [Arts Council Wales](#), [Creative Scotland](#), [National Lottery Heritage Fund](#), [The Space](#), and [Wellcome Trust](#). In addition to this, the majority of our data came from [PressReader](#)'s catalogue of newspapers and magazines. We also supplemented the data by canvassing members of the CoSTAR Network for any significant projects we had missed while undertaking our desk research.

For each of these sources we searched for any mentions of key search terms within a 2006-2024 time span. Those terms are: 'augmented reality' and AR, 'extended reality' and XR, 'game engine', immersive, 'mixed reality', 'virtual production' and VP, and 'virtual reality' and VR. We then manually assessed the relevance of the search results before extracting data across multiple fields.

The final dataset took the form of a spreadsheet with fields for:

- the date the data was gathered,
- member of the research team who collected the data,
- source of the data (e.g. National Lottery Heritage Fund, Pressreader),
- search term used,
- URL of project website or news article,
- name of project,
- associated individuals,
- associated organisations,
- description of the project,
- funding source,
- funding amount,
- start year,
- date span,
- location (town or city).

As the data came from different sources, including press coverage, it was not always possible to complete all these fields.

We then augmented the dataset with further data points to enable us to answer our research questions. To ascertain the geographic distribution of XR projects we used city and postcode data to locate latitude and longitude data as well as the respective UK nation. To better understand the technologies used and their associated use cases we manually annotated each project with the type of technology (AR, Immersive, MR, VR, XR), the use case for that technology (e.g. exhibition, film, game, performance), and the topic of the project (e.g. history,

music, science). To be able to compare the priorities of these XR projects with those funded by UKRI we manually annotated whether each project mentioned sustainability, equality, diversity & inclusion, artificial intelligence or heritage.

This resulted in a dataset of 380 XR projects taking place in the UK between 2006 and 2024.

The dataset is available for [download](#) from Zenodo under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

We also conducted desk research to fill in one area we knew was lacking: VP studios in the UK. For this subset, we sought to locate data in the following categories for each studio:

- URL,
- name of studio,
- associated individuals,
- associated organisation,
- description of studio,
- funding source,
- funding amount,
- whether the website has VP specs,
- location,
- full address,
- postcode.

As the landscape of VP studios changes quickly, with companies often emerging and ceasing trading within a short period of time, we limited our research to studios that were active at the time of conducting this research: September-December 2025.

This resulted in a separate spreadsheet with data for 41 VP studios in the UK active at the time of research and publication in Spring 2026.

Limitations of the Data

It should be noted that the public and private funding landscapes are complex with much overlap. In some cases, projects may have been joint funded by UKRI and another body. We have done our best to distinguish funders but that has not been possible in every case due to limited descriptions provided.

When using the internet to research phenomena between 2006 and 2024, it can be expected that the available digital records will skew towards the end of that window as data is increasingly shared online but digital artefacts are ephemeral. In fact, 25% of web pages posted between 2013 and 2023 have now vanished (Stokel-Walker, 2024). We expected to find an increase in projects using XR technologies over time and more recent activity in VP, given the technology's recent maturation, but assume that this increase is heightened by the relative unavailability of data earlier in that window. It is likely that reducing costs for equipment, and technologies maturing, are also factors. It has become a truism that "not everything that can be counted counts and not everything that counts can be counted" (Toye, 2015). It should be noted that this dataset cannot claim to be comprehensive and the data used in this report is that which is both available and was uncovered using our structured search strategy. Our method can be used in future research to undertake comparable analysis and we have made our dataset openly available for this purpose.

Software and Packages Used

The resulting dataset was augmented, visualised and analysed using the following tools:

- [Flourish](#) for the generation of geographical maps
- [GPS Coordinates](#) for finding latitude and longitudes
- Microsoft Excel (Version 2510 Build 16.0.19328.20244) for all other data analysis and visualisation.

Research Ethics Approval

Research ethics approval was obtained from Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh. This research is part of the CoSTAR Foresight Lab's activities, funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council ([AH/Y007433/1](#)).

OVERVIEW OF XR PROJECTS

We found 380 projects using XR technologies in the UK between 2006 and 2024 and 41 virtual production studios active in 2025. This section focuses on the 380 projects; the VP studios are explored in a later section.

Technologies

The dataset contains details about AR, VR and MR technologies, also about projects more generally described as employing XR or other immersive technologies. The most frequently used technology is AR, then VR (see Table 1). Other technologies or platforms mentioned once or twice are digital twins, esports, metaverse, Second Life, and VP.

Table 1. Frequency of technologies mentioned by XR projects, 2006-2024.

Technology	Number of projects
AR	171
VR	137
Immersive	37
XR	16
MR	10
Other	9

Use Cases

These technologies are used for multiple purposes, most frequently AR trails, physical games, and VR experiences and performances (see Table 2). Other use cases include venues built for XR, interactive books, and fairground rides.

Table 2. Frequency of use cases for XR technologies in projects, 2006-2024.

Use case	Number of projects
Trail	73
Game	51
Experience	48
Performance	39
App	37
Installation	35
Exhibition	34
Film	15
Training	8
Other	40

Themes

The themes of the XR media projects were less easy to classify. The 380 XR projects span multiple themes, which have been placed into five categories: history and local interest, nature and science, performance and storytelling, visual art, and other topics (see Table 3). The history and local interest category includes apps, trails, and experiences related to buildings, sites and people of historic and cultural interest. Nature and science includes dinosaur events, AR trails related to science and nature and exhibitions. Performance and storytelling covers theatre, dance, music and comedy. The visual art theme involves exhibitions and installations that use XR technologies. The ‘other’ category includes fashion shows, films, games, esports and other activities and events that do not fit into the other categories, including, a VR Santa sleigh ride, a digitally enhanced playground, and an AR Easter egg hunt.

Table 3. Themes covered by XR technologies in projects, 2006-2024.

Theme	Number of projects
History and local interest	103
Nature and science	53
Performance and storytelling	53
Visual art	31
Other	140

Timelines

The XR projects took place between 2006 and 2024 with an increase in the frequency of projects most years over time (see Figure 1). The steepest rises occurred from 2015-16 and 2020-2023. 2024 shows a slight reduction in XR projects from 2023, although this could be explained by a lag in reporting.

Figure 1. Number of XR projects per year, 2006-2024.

We looked at the technologies mentioned in descriptions of each project and categorised them as: AR, VR, and other, which aggregates immersive, MR, XR, digital twins, esports, metaverse, Second Life, and VP. Looking at the frequency of mentions of each technology per year, while initially all technology types were similarly frequent between 2006 and 2013, AR and VR became the dominant technology types,

eclipsing mentions of the other technologies combined (see Figure 2).

The delivery of AR technologies began to become more frequent after 2014 with a peak in 2022. An increase in VR can be seen after 2014 with a peak in 2023. The other technologies became more frequent after 2017 with a peak in 2023 that does not match either the peak of AR or VR. From 2022 to 2023 there is a reversal in the frequency of AR and VR: AR drops from being mentioned in 39 projects in 2022 to 28 in 2023 while VR increases from being mentioned in 12 projects in 2022 to 22 projects in 2023. This is followed by a return to more consistent numbers of AR and VR projects in 2024.

Figure 2. Instances of XR technologies mentioned in projects each year, 2006-2024. Some data points are labelled for clarity.

Geographic Spread of Projects

Of the 380 projects, 305 have locatable latitudes and longitudes within the UK. The remaining 75 projects were located across whole nations (for example, UK-wide, Scotland-wide) or took place across multiple locations.

The projects were spread across the UK at 142 unique locations (see Figure 3), with concentrations in London, Cardiff, Bristol and Central

Image courtesy of the Centre for Creative and Immersive Extended Reality ([CCIXR](#)), University of Portsmouth; photographer: Rob Hobbs.

Scotland, as well as a lot of activity in the Midlands and North of England. There are noticeably fewer projects in Northern Ireland and East Anglia, and slightly fewer in the North of Scotland, central Wales, the West of England and North-West England.

Figure 3. Locations of XR projects in the UK, 2006-2024. The dots on the map represent the locations of XR projects and the size of the dots represents the number of projects in each location. The UK's four capital cities have been labelled for reference.

A comparison of the number of XR projects in each of the UK's four nations with their population (see Table 4) reveals that Scotland has a proportionally higher number of XR projects relative to its population, England has a proportionally lower number of XR projects, and Northern Ireland and Wales have similar proportions of XR projects.

Table 4. UK nations' number of projects and population size. Population data sourced from [Office for National Statistics](#).

Nation	Number of XR projects	% of projects	% of UK population residing in that nation	Difference
England	223	73.11475	84.61155	-11.4968
Northern Ireland	4	1.311475	2.782643	-1.47117
Scotland	58	19.01639	8.006329	11.01006
Wales	20	6.557377	4.599473	1.957904

Distribution of Themes Across the UK

305 projects have both identifiable location and themes data. The themes were relatively evenly distributed around the UK (see Figure 4). The history and local interest projects (pink dots, 84 instances) were prevalent throughout the UK, including in areas that do not have a high concentration of other XR projects, such as the North of Scotland, the Scottish Borders and the South-West of England. Nature and science projects (light blue, 35 instances) were relatively infrequent, with notable occurrences in Hull for a [theatre show that incorporated virtual reality](#) and a [VR experience about air pollution devices and airborne infectious diseases](#), as well as Yorkshire and the Humber where [Sheffield DocFest](#) included immersive experiences in its programme. Performance and storytelling (yellow, 34 instances) was most prevalent in the cities of Cardiff, Edinburgh, Birmingham and Bristol. Visual art (purple, 31 instances) was concentrated in London. The 'other' category, (dark blue, 121 instances), encompasses fashion shows, films, games, esports and other events. It had higher concentrations in London, Nottingham, Glasgow and the Midlands and North of England where, for example, the [Sunderland Business Improvement District](#) has funded three seasonal AR trails for Christmas and Easter.

Figure 4. Locations of XR projects by theme, 2006-2024. The dots on the map represent the locations of XR projects, the size of the dots represents the numbers of XR projects in each location, and the colour of each dot represents the theme of the XR project. The UK's four capital cities have been labelled for reference.

There were 58 projects in London. London has 13% of the UK's population and 19% of XR projects with an identifiable location or 15% of all projects in the dataset (Population data sourced from [Office for National Statistics](#)), so the number of projects in London is slightly higher than expected. This perhaps reflects the burgeoning tourist market for XR experiences, rather than the local populations (Kumlu et al., 2024).

The concentration of projects in London makes it difficult to see on the map above. There are projects in London across all five categories: history and local interest, nature and science, performance and storytelling, visual art, and other (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Themes of XR projects in London, 2006-2024.

XR FUNDING
LANDSCAPE
BEYOND UKRI

In this section, we give an overview of funding and major funders in the XR space. Around 52% (199 out of 380) of the projects we located named their funding source and 24% (90 out of 380) provided funding amounts.

As mentioned above, it should be noted that the public and private funding landscapes are complex with much overlap. In some cases, projects may have been joint funded by UKRI and another body. We have done our best to distinguish funders but that has not been possible in every case.

Funding Over Time

The projects with funding data started between 2006 and 2024, that is, across the whole period we address in this report. The funding amounts ranged from around £5,000 to £13m.

The data shows very small amounts of funding for projects between 2006 and 2015 and an increase in funding from 2016 onwards with an anomalously large amount of funding in 2016 (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Funding for XR projects each year, 2006-2024.

Large Funding Awards

Large amounts of funding (over £1m) were granted to 10 projects in 2016, 2019, 2021, 2022 and 2023. The projects awarded over £1m (see Table 5) take the form of large-scale development of heritage and nature attractions ([Invisible Worlds at the Eden Project](#), [Norwich Castle, Garnock landscape](#), [The Brunel Museum](#), [railway heritage at Hopetown](#), the [Scottish Crannog Centre](#), [Coventry Guildhall](#), and the [Loch Ness Centre](#)), the research and development of VR software ([Retinize](#)), and a [funding pot for companies investing in creative technologies in Cornwall](#).

Table 5. XR projects in the UK with funding over £1m, 2016-2023

Year	Project name	Funder	Funding Amount
2016	Invisible Worlds	Wellcome Trust	£1,799,752
2016	Norwich Castle: Royal Palace Reborn	National Lottery Heritage Fund	£13,412,376
2016	All-ability access to Garnock land-scape	National Lottery Heritage Fund	£1,505,000
2019	The Brunel Museum Reinvented	National Lottery Heritage Fund	£2,302,400
2021	Hopetown: celebrating the North East's railway heritage	National Lottery Heritage Fund	£3,264,232
2022	Retinize	Sure Valley Ventures UK Software Technology Fund, Bertram van Munster, Elise Doganieri	£2,000,000
2022	Scottish Crannog Centre	Scottish Government	£2,300,000
2022	Coventry Guildhall AR tour	National Lottery Heritage Fund	£1,800,000
2023	Funding pot for companies investing in creative technologies in Cornwall	Cornwall and the Isles of Scilly Local Enterprise Partnership	£1,000,000
2023	Loch Ness Centre	Continuum Attractions	£1,500,000

These 10 projects were funded by a non-departmental public body (National Lottery Heritage Fund, 5 projects), charitable trust (the Wellcome Trust, 1 project), governmental body (Scottish Government, 1 project), local enterprise partnership (Cornwall and the Isles of Scilly Local Enterprise Partnership, 1 project), commercial entity (Continuum Attractions, 1 project), and a collaboration between an investment fund and two tv producers (Sure Valley Ventures UK Software Technology Fund, Bertram van Munster, and Elise Doganieri, 1 project).

Funders

Out of the 380 projects funding data was publicly available for 199 of them. There were 163 unique funders with some funding multiple projects. These funders operate across public, private and nonprofit sectors (see Table 6). The most frequent type of funder was commercial entities, followed by community development, Business Improvement District or Local Enterprise Partnerships, local authorities, and arts organisation, venue or event. The 'other' category includes broadcasters (BBC and Channel 5), investment firms, individuals and a zoo.

Table 6. Types of funder of XR projects in the UK, 2006-2024

Funder type	Number of funders
Commercial entities	33
Community development, Business Improvement Districts or Local Enterprise Partnerships	23
Local authorities	20
Arts organisations, venues or events	19
Governmental bodies or other government funding schemes	17
Non-departmental public bodies	15
Charities and philanthropic entities	11
Academic institutions	7
Other	18

Within these types of funders, we looked at which individual funders funded the most projects. The most prolific individual funders were National Lottery Heritage Fund (non-departmental public body; 30 projects), Wellcome Trust (charities and philanthropic entities; 30), Arts Council England (non-departmental public body; 17), Creative Scotland (non-departmental public body; 6), BBC (other – broadcaster; 4), Scottish Government (Governmental bodies or other government funding schemes; 3) and UK Shared Prosperity Fund (Governmental bodies or other government funding schemes; 3) (see Table 7). The remaining organisations funded between 1 and 2 projects each.

Table 7. Most frequent funders of XR projects in the UK, 2006-2024

Funder	Number of projects
National Lottery Heritage Fund	30
Wellcome Trust	30
Arts Council England	17
Creative Scotland	6
BBC	4
Scottish Government	3
UK Shared Prosperity Fund	3

Funder Overview

In this section we break down the types of funders and the types of projects they funded.

Commercial entities

Many of the projects mentioned in this report did not receive funding from a public body or charity. They were commercial ventures, including public limited companies who possibly received venture capital or other forms of investment that are not transparent to the public. One of the most popular uses for XR technology by commercial entities was VR games and activities, such as escape rooms, racing simulators and puzzles (for example, [Boom Battle Bar](#)) as well as attractions like the AR-enhanced Magical Forest at [Legoland](#) and a VR installation at [Finlaggan Visitor Centre](#) funded in part by Lagavulin Distillery.

Community development, Business Improvement Districts and Local Enterprise Partnerships

Community development, Business Improvement Districts and Local Enterprise Partnerships are consortia designed to develop businesses and community facilities in a local area, such as Love Loughborough BID, which funded an [AR Easter egg hunt](#), Our Union Street, which funded a range of [AR activities in central Aberdeen](#), and the Cornwall and the Isles of Scilly Local Enterprise Partnership, which provided a [funding source for companies investing in creative technologies](#).

Local authorities

Various local councils funded XR projects, often taking the form of AR trails, such as Cardiff Council's [Spooky augmented reality Halloween Trail](#), North East Lincolnshire Council's [Cleethorpes AR dinosaur trail](#), and DCSDC's Derry Halloween City Centre Arts Cultural Funding's [Derry Ancient Spirit Hunt](#) to help raise funds for Foyle Search and Rescue. In addition to AR trails, there were efforts to make local areas more attractive, such as the [Future Paisley Exhibition](#) funded by Renfrewshire Council and OneRen, and [Wallsend town centre regeneration](#) funded by the North of Tyne Combined Authority.

Arts organisations, venues and events

Individual arts organisations, venues and events like festivals provided funding for XR projects, such as the Welsh National Opera's [Magic Butterfly](#), supported by Sasakawa Foundation, which included VR, and [Minnie Stynker](#), a book with interactive AR elements; those elements were commissioned by The Space through Arts Council England funding.

Governmental bodies and other government funding schemes

The Scottish, UK and Welsh governments contributed funding to some sizeable projects, including the [Scottish Crannog Centre](#) (£2.3m), the University of Portsmouth for [creating skills, boosting communities and benefitting visitor and cultural economy](#) from the UK Community Renewal Fund (£628,000) as well as Portsmouth City Council, [The Mary Rose Trust](#), [Spinnaker Tower](#), [Victorious Festival](#), [Gosport Borough Council](#), [Aspex Visual Arts Trust](#) and [The D-Day Story](#), and, finally, the [Explorer Trail LLO](#), an AR trail, from the Welsh Government's Valleys Regional Park scheme (£185,000).

The Government of Northern Ireland was not directly named in the XR projects we located. However, they contributed substantially to the creation of Studio Ulster, a £72m investment into virtual production facilities at Belfast Harbour Studios, part-funded through the [Belfast Region City Deal](#).

Non-departmental public bodies

The [National Lottery Heritage Fund](#) is a prolific funder of XR, funding projects using XR technologies from 2014 to 2024 with funding amounts ranging from approximately £6,000 to £13m. The projects involved a range of different technologies and applications with relevance to

heritage.

Several of the projects involved the development of augmented reality apps and trails for site-specific enhancement of heritage sites, such as an [app for self-guided walks](#) around Loughborough Junction that delivers fictional and real stories from World War One developed for the Imperial War Museums.

The funding also went to several virtual reality projects that enabled visitors to experience simulations of physical locations via a VR headset that they could not otherwise access, such as [Corby's steel industry](#) and stories set around the [River Garnock](#) with support from the Nature Scot Green Infrastructure Fund as part of the [Places That We Know](#) project.

The largest single funding award by the National Lottery Heritage Fund was made to Norfolk County Council for the development of the heritage destination of [Norwich Castle](#), including audio-visual projections inspired by medieval art and a digitally-recreated Norman Norwich, which can be accessed through virtual reality headsets.

[Creative Scotland](#) funded a number of immersive projects involving convergent technologies between 2020 and 2024 with funding ranging from approximately £5,000 to £45,000. These projects include immersive performances and workshops, such as [Weathervanes](#) by Jian Yi, an immersive-multimedia exhibit and ritual dance theatre experience produced by Journey to the East Productions in association with Summerhall, Eclipse and Tramway.

[Arts Council England](#) funded, among others, the project Brainwave Immersive Installation in 2020, which resulted in the art installation [Res Nodus](#) by artist Ashley Middleton, which incorporated brain-computer interface technologies.

The data available for [Arts Council Northern Ireland](#) and [Arts Council Wales](#) did not contain details of the funded projects, only project names and funding amounts, and so it could not be determined whether they related to XR technologies.

Charities and philanthropic entities

The charities and philanthropic institutions funding XR include the [Art Fund](#), [Historic Royal Palaces](#), and [Bloomberg Philanthropies](#).

[The Wellcome Trust](#) has funded XR projects since 2006 with funding values ranging from approximately £6,000 to £1.8m. The majority of their awards were made for immersive installations, such as [Lexicon – Dyslexia: sound, sign and sense](#) by Andrew Lewis of Bangor University, a 360-degree spatial sound experience designed to highlight dyslexia and draw attention to some of the current theoretical thinking around the role played by aural, phonological and phonographic processing. Their largest single funding award was made to the Eden Trust for the [Eden Project](#), which has multiple immersive, virtual reality and augmented reality features.

Academic institutions

Several universities and schools funded XR projects, including the University of the West of Scotland's [V-Art](#) gallery and the University of York, which funded the [Awesome Animals Safari](#) AR trail through its Young XR Fund. Although several academic institutions contributed towards XR projects in our dataset, the presence of academic institutions is much greater in projects funded by UKRI (see '[UK Innovation in Immersive XR Technologies for screen, performance and digital entertainment: UKRI funding trends and insights \(2006–2024\)](#)'). And, of course, the [CoSTAR Network](#) brings together academic and industry collaborators for a range of projects involving XR technologies, which are beyond the scope of this report.

In this section we discuss each type of XR technology and how it has been implemented and developed between 2006 and 2024 in the UK. VP will be explored in more detail in the next section.

Image of augmented reality children's picture book Minny Stynker courtesy of [The Space](#); photographer: Artur Tixiliski.

TECHNOLOGIES: AR, VR, XR

Augmented Reality

Since 2016, AR apps for smartphones, such as [Pokémon Go](#), have become popular. AR is defined as “a medium in which information is added to the physical world in registration with the world” (Craig, 2013). What this means practically is that participants usually use their own device (a smartphone) and download an app that delivers digital content related to or stimulated by physical objects. These objects may be QR codes, artworks or vistas.

Alan B. Craig (2013) further describes the essential features of AR: digital information is superimposed on a view of the physical world, the information is displayed in relation to the physical world, the information displayed is dependent on the location of the real world and the physical perspective of the participant in the physical world, and the experience is to some degree interactive in that the participant can make changes to the information, even if only by moving their phone.

The dataset contains data on 171 projects and services that use AR, even though some of them do not exhibit this last feature of interactivity. The most predominant use cases for AR we found were apps, often tethered to a physical trail.

AR Apps

We found 33 AR apps starting between 2011 and 2024. These apps were created to provide augmented content in relation to multiple different topics, with the most frequent ones being historical events, locations of historical interest, and entertainment such as storytelling.

Some AR apps are tied to a physical location, but some can be experienced anywhere, for example, in the participant’s home, and some are designed for use throughout the whole of the UK (and beyond). For example, there are apps that use the Global Positioning System’s (GPS) data to locate the participant and then impose map data onto the images they can see through their phone camera, such as [AR City by Blippar](#), which augments in-camera images with 3D directions and street names.

AR Trails

Our dataset uncovered 69 augmented reality trails around the UK with the earliest occurring in 2013 and the majority of them between 2021 and 2024. They covered a wide range of topics in multiple locations across the UK.

These are usually self-guided tours where participants download an app to their smartphone and follow a pre-designated path or explore a space in a more self-directed manner. The AR content may be supplementary (in the case of adding information about an object or location) or interactive (in the case of overlaying multimedia content over a background image of an object, artwork or view).

[Street Stories Stirling](#) featured a series of artworks by local artists, which, when viewed through the related app, triggered an animated version of the artwork.

[The Bomb Sight](#) app, made by the University of Portsmouth, and National Archives, with funding from JISC, allowed the user to use their camera to view newer buildings in London and, using GPS within the phone, returned information about the World War Two bombs that fell within 300 metres of the user’s position.

There were many different topics for AR trails, but one of the most common was history-based, interpreting locations, people and stories from the past. These tended to attract funding from local councils and tourism initiatives as well as national arts councils and the National Lottery Heritage Fund. The other most popular theme was activities, usually for children, often tied to events like Christmas, Halloween or Easter. These also often received funding from local councils or were tied to commercial ventures like [Chester Zoo](#) or [Legoland](#).

The AR trails in the dataset had a wide geographic spread (see Figure 7), likely due to the low technology costs involved in creating a trail: the

Image courtesy of [Displace Studio](#), a mixed reality performance studio; photographer: Julian Hughes.

largest expense is smartphones, which the users are generally expected to bring themselves. The 69 trails took place at 48 different locations. Most locations had only one trail; Sunderland had the most with four trails. The trails were located across all four UK nations with higher concentrations in the Midlands, North of England and South-East England.

Figure 7. Locations of AR trails across the UK, 2006 -2024. The dots on the map represent the locations of AR trails and the size of the dots represents the numbers of AR trails in each location. The UK's four capital cities have been labelled for reference.

Virtual Reality

The Oculus Rift VR headset had its first consumer release in 2016 (Stapleton, 2016) and since then consumers have had access to virtual worlds for the purposes of education, training, healthcare, design and architecture, entertainment, gaming, fitness, creative expression, travel and other simulated experiences. Virtual reality describes an extensible, virtual space to simulate the presence of the user in that space. This is effected through interactive devices such as goggles, headsets, gloves, or body suits, which both send and receive information to allow the user to move around and interact with aspects of the virtual space. A VR headset is a typical way of engaging with virtual reality spaces.

Samuel Greengard describes how “in family rooms, offices, and research labs around the world, people are using special goggles or head-mounted displays – along with haptic gloves and other apparatus – to venture inside a computer-generated world that convincingly mimics our physical world” (Greengard, 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the introduction of VR to enable users to access places they could not due to social distancing and temporary closures (Baía & Ashmore, 2022).

We found 137 VR projects in the UK between 2006 and 2024, with a marked increase from 2014 and peaks in 2017 and 2023. The most predominant use cases for VR we found were for taking part in virtual exhibitions, experiences, games, and performances.

Exhibitions

VR technologies have been used to create virtual exhibitions that can combine multisensory and interactive elements. We found 17 exhibitions using VR between 2015 and 2024.

[The Fourth Wall](#) by John Walter, guest artist at Paisley Art Institute’s 131st annual exhibition and commissioned by the Look Again Festival, used VR to create imaginary landscapes combining sound, music, text and colourful imagery. In 2020 [Carmarthen School of Art’s Graduate Show](#) harnessed VR’s capabilities to stage their graduate show at a time when physical distancing was enforced.

The National Lottery Heritage Fund and academic institutions were among the most frequent funders of these exhibitions.

Experiences

One of the most often used descriptions of VR activities is ‘experiences’. These projects enable participants to experience places and activities they could not otherwise. There are 41 VR experiences in our dataset, taking place between 2008 and 2024.

VR experiences have been used in the heritage and tourism sectors to allow visitors to experience simulations of the past, such as a reconstructed digital model of the fort at Fort William in 1746 at the time of the [Siege of Fort William](#) (developed by the West Highland Museum) and a series of VR videos showing different aspects of life on the frontlines at the [First World War Battle of Passchendaele](#) from The Royal British Legion and historian Dan Snow. The Legion also made available 1,000 free cardboard VR headsets. These headsets are used in conjunction with a smartphone and negate the need for a VR headset, getting around a noted reluctance of consumers to buy their own headsets (Green et al., 2021).

These projects were often funded by heritage funders, such as National Lottery Grants for Heritage, local heritage organisations, and national heritage organisations, such as Historic England, as well as government funds.

Games

In the commercial sector, since 2016 multiple VR arcade-style venues have been established. We found 29 venues offering a range of VR games and activities, such as escape rooms, racing simulators and puzzles.

For example, [Zero Latency](#) offered multiple scenarios that can be experienced in groups at six locations around England. These scenarios covered zombie outbreaks, haunted houses and space combat. [VR World](#), located in Maidstone, offered a more traditional arcade experience with tokens exchanged for playing VR games, as well as VR escape rooms.

Performances

VR technology has been incorporated into multiple types of performance, predominantly music, theatre and dance, but also a show by comedian [Ed Byrne](#).

These performances can take the form of physical productions that have been filmed for later presentation in VR, productions that were designed solely to be experienced in VR, or multimedia performances.

The show [Facades by Displace Studio](#) created a performance and performance space that the viewer could move around in and experience from different angles, supported by Arts Council England, De Montfort University, Near Now, and the University of Nottingham. Music from across the genres has been given the VR treatment, such as the [Philharmonia Orchestra and Nicola Benedetti performing Ralph Vaughan Williams's The Lark Ascending](#) as part of Edinburgh International Festival and [Biffy Clyro's song 'Flammable'](#), which was viewable on VR headsets in a pop-up 'Hypercube' at UK music festivals in 2016.

Arts councils were a frequent funder of this type of project along with commercial media producers.

Mixed reality and other immersive technologies

As can be seen from the discussions of AR and VR technologies, there are overlaps in both the technologies and their use cases. The projects in our dataset that are not clearly AR, VP or VR fall into the more general categories of immersive, XR, and mixed reality (MR). There are 72 projects in this category.

The 10 MR projects occurred between 2018 and 2024 and covered a range of use cases, such as films, games, installations and performances. For example, a performance by [A-V artist Halina Rice](#), who contacted art colleges in London looking for collaborators, included music and both programmed and real-time visuals with projections and lighting.

37 projects come under the heading of immersive. These projects took place between 2007 and 2024 and covered use cases such as films, installations and performances. Installations were the most popular use case for projects described as immersive, such as [Lexicon – Dyslexia: sound, sign and sense](#) by Andrew Lewis.

16 projects fell into the broad category of XR. These projects took place between 2009 and 2024 and covered many use cases, such as apps, films and games. Some projects defied easy categorisation as they were support schemes (such as the [Immex City Digital Catapult programme](#)) or training events (such as [Enabling XR Enterprise](#)). These projects were funded by large, often national or governmental funding schemes such as the UK Shared Prosperity Fund, UK Community Renewal Fund and the Welsh Government.

The remaining 9 projects in this category related to very specific technologies and platforms, including a [concert by Robbie Williams](#) on the Metaverse platform LightCycle, a [concert by the Royal Liverpool Philharmonic](#) in the long-running multiplayer virtual world Second Life, the use of digital twins by the National Trust for Scotland and app developers GeoGeo to [map heritage and archaeological sites](#) and build immersive virtual tours, and the use of virtual production by Channel 5 in the creation of the tv series ['Dinosaur' with Stephen Fry](#).

Image courtesy of Displace Studio of [Facades](#), an immersive virtual reality dance theatre experience.

VIRTUAL PRODUCTION

In this section we turn the spotlight onto virtual production as one implementation of convergent XR technologies (real-time rendering via game engines, LED video walls, and motion capture technology) that has become prominent.

While the use of green or blue screen technology has been familiar to many audiences for several years, VP replaces green or blue screens with a wall of LED screens that display backdrops that are generated in real-time using video game technology, such as Unreal Engine. Actors, directors and cinematographers can see the backdrop visuals in real time, cameras are synced to what is displayed on the LED screens, and physical and digital props are connected so that VP combines physical and digital elements to “harness the power of virtualising technologies to create digital environments in, and through which film and television can be made” (Willment & Swords, 2023, p. 4).

In our previous report we found 38 projects funded by UKRI between 2014 and 2024 that related to virtual production. The current landscape of VP in the UK is comprised of further non-UKRI-funded activity and thriving commercial studios and companies, which are interconnected. We found 41 active VP studios in 2025 located in the UK, mostly private companies, although some are university-funded studios and training facilities (see Table 8).

Image courtesy of [MARS Volume](#), a virtual production environment in London provided by Bild Studios.

Studio Name	City	First half of post-code
ARRI Stage London	London	UB8
Broadley Studio	London	NW1
Brooklands Studio	Weybridge	KT13
Capture Studios	Tamworth	B78
Centre for Creative and Im-mersive Extended Reality (CCIXR)	Portsmouth	PO1
CUBE Studio at The Lyric, Hammersmith	London	W6
CUBE Studio At Windsor College	Windsor	SL4
CUBE Studio East London	London	E3
CUBE Studio LED Stage for Commercials & Film	London	NW10
CUBE Studio Maidenhead	Maidenhead	SL6
CUBE StudioX at Mount Pleasant	London	WC1X
CUBE StudioX at The Studio Barn	Chippenham	SN14
Distortion Studios	Bristol	BS4
Film Soho	London	W1F
fivefold studios	Bridgend	CF35
Garden Studios	London	NW10
Haddenham Studio	Haddenham	HP17
ILM	London	WC1N
Imaginarium Studios	London	W1W
LAMDA	London	W14
Linney	Mansfield	NG18
Mars Volume	London	HA4
Nightsky Studios	Coatbridge	ML5
Nottingham Trent University Virtual Production Studio	Nottingham	NG1
Quite Brilliant	London	TW1
Racquet Studios	Lewes	BN7
Ramaz Studios	London	SE2
Ramaz Studios	London	W1D
Rebellion Film Studios Rebellion Film Studios	Didcot	OX11

Recode XR	Manchester	M12
Silvertown Studios: LED Stage Silvertown St Marks	London	E16
Silvertown Studios: On-Location Mobile Virtual Production	N/A	N/A
Silvertown Studios: Virtual Production Studio Silvertown Riverside	London	E16
Studio Ulster	Belfast	BT3
Sugar Studios	London	SE10
UCA Virtual Production and Mixed Reality Studio	Farnham	GU9
University of Nottingham Virtual & Immersive Production Studio	Nottingham	NG7
Vectar Project	Stockport	SK4
Virtual Production Studios by 80six	Slough	SL2
Warner Bros Leavesden Studios	Leavesden	WD25
XPLOR	South Kirkby	WF9

Commercial Studios

The landscape of virtual production studios in the UK is dominated by commercial studios that provide studio space and technologies (and often crew) for the production of advertisements, music videos, tv shows and films, from independent facilities like [fivefold studios](#) in Wales to the UK bases for international companies like [Warner Brothers](#). Some companies also offer mobile VP set-ups that can be moved to other locations (e.g. [Nightsky Studios](#) based in Coatbridge, [Silvertown Studios](#) based in London).

University-owned Studios and Training Facilities

Within our dataset there are several studios that also function as training facilities. These include facilities located at higher education institutions (e.g. Nottingham Trent University, University of Nottingham, London Academy of Music & Dramatic Art, UCA Virtual Production and Mixed Reality Studio, and the Centre for Creative and Immersive Extended Reality at the University of Portsmouth). Some of the commercial studios also offer training courses (e.g. [Mars Volume](#)).

It should be noted that other academic institutions, especially arts schools, likely provide training in XR technologies as part of their course offerings but these were not captured in our dataset.

TV Corporations

The current television production model involves independent production companies developing and creating series that are then sold to (or were commissioned by) broadcasters and streamers like BBC, Sky, ITV, Channel 4, Netflix and Amazon Prime. These productions often make use of independent studios, including many of the studios in our dataset.

Additionally, broadcasters often have their own studio facilities. Virtual studios are used by BBC ([BBC Cymru Wales Production Facilities](#) in Cardiff) and Sky ([Sky Production Studios](#) in Isleworth, London) for the in-house production of news, sport and game show content. These virtual studios differ from virtual production studios or LED volumes. In a virtual studio, the majority of the backdrop and set are green screens with camera tracking and rendering in real time. The full picture of presenters and digital effects can be seen through a monitor. This differs from LED volumes where the green screen is replaced by a real-time rendering of visuals that can be seen by everyone on set. Virtual studios are beyond the scope of this report.

Example: British Broadcasting Corporation

The studios used for virtual production – and the crew as well – are connected in terms of their funding coming from both UKRI and private investment. This is indicative of greater connection across the creative industries. As an example, the BBC has been using virtual sets since the 1990s (Popkin, 1997). In our previous report we found that between 2007 and 2024 the BBC was involved in 28 UKRI-funded XR projects, including 3 VP projects in 2018 and 2022. Now, it broadcasts series and films made using VP, such as [The People's Piazza: A History of Covent Garden](#) (2022), which was produced by Uplands Television, StoryFutures Academy, and Familiar Spot, of which Storyfutures is supported by the UKRI-AHRC [Audience of the Future](#) programme.

The BBC has been recognised as “an anchor institution in the UK’s creative R&D ecosystem” (Mateos-Garcia, 2021, p. 5) and for its role in collaborative software development (Mateos-Garcia, 2015), both pushing forward innovative technologies and working with multiple institutions across commercial and government-funded spheres.

Location

London is the epicentre for commercial VP studios. Of the 41 active studios in the UK, 18 are located in London. Other studios were located in and near Cardiff, Bristol, Manchester, Nottingham and West Yorkshire. We located one studio in Northern Ireland (Belfast) and one in Scotland (Coatbridge) (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Map of commercial VP studios in the UK in 2025. The dots on the map represent the locations of VP studios and the size of the dots represents the number of studios in each location. The UK’s four capital cities have been labelled for reference.

Year of Inception

The founding year for 31 of the 41 VP studios still active in 2025 is visualised in Figure 9. This is the year that the studio first advertised having VP capabilities, although some studios existed prior to this using different production methods. The studios were all founded in 2021 or later, with most studios founded in 2023. The figure for 2025 may be incomplete as the data for this report was collected before the 2025 year end.

Figure 9. Number of UK VP studios opened per year, 2021-2025.

XR: A STORY OF TECH ADOPTION

This section focuses on the adoption, proliferation and funding / support of various XR technologies in the UK.

Innovation is central to the creative industries (Gohoungodji & Amara, 2023), with constant innovation leading to new products and services. The creative industries have been described as “permanent innovators” (Bathelt, et al., 2017, p. 6) where “innovation and knowledge creation [are] the central processes that trigger fundamental changes in economies and societies” (Bathelt, et al., 2017, p. 2). This innovation can be understood as the continual “development of new technologies or the adaptation of existing technologies in a novel way” (Siepel et al., 2022), and one way of conceptualising such development and adaptation is in terms of tech adoption.

Tech adoption categorises the uptake of new technologies into five stages: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards (Rogers, 2003). The data in this report shows the early adoption of XR technologies from 2006 onwards. These first forays into XR by early adopters made use of the already widely-used platform of Second Life (for a [concert by the Royal Liverpool Philharmonic](#) and a [replica of the Baltic Mill gallery](#)), a replica [VR blast furnace](#) at the Summerlee Museum of Scottish Industrial Life, and a [Virtual Maidstone football stadium](#). These projects show a range of use cases and organisations: there is no one clear early adopter in terms of sectors, use cases, funders or technologies.

Augmented Reality

From 2010 AR projects make up a significant proportion of all XR projects, comprising 44% of the 380 projects we found. They had a clear increase from 2019, a peak in 2022 and a slight decline between 2022 and 2023 before a resurgence in 2024 (see Figure 2). The most frequent use cases were apps and trails. These are low-cost initiatives that can be implemented by local tourist or heritage organisations as well as commercial entities. With minimal set up (an app and potentially visual markers in physical locations), the onus is on the user to own a smartphone and download the app. The use of AR apps increased after 2021, likely prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic as AR trails are usually located outside and therefore can still be used during times of social distancing, as well as the increase of smartphone users.

Virtual Reality

VR projects are present in the dataset from 2006. They had a steep increase after 2014, a slight decrease after 2017, a peak in 2023 and a decrease in 2024 (see Figure 2). They comprise 35% of the 380 projects we found. The most frequent use cases were exhibitions, experiences, games and performances, accessed through a VR headset. From 2017, VR projects are frequently represented in our dataset; this coincides with the commercial release of the Oculus Rift VR headset in 2016 (Stapleton, 2016). Although VR headsets have come down in price since then, there are still known barriers to their adoption (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2025), partly arising from constantly evolving sensor technology (Yang, 2023).

Mixed Reality and Other Immersive Technologies

XR technologies other than AR and VR account for 18% of the 380 total projects with the most frequent use cases being installations and performances (see Figure 2). The evidence indicates that XR technologies are being more widely adopted in sectors outside of the creative industries (Ivey, 2024).

Virtual Production

One of the earlier studios to use VP technology was Imaginarium Studios, formed by actor and director Andy Serkis, which had VP capability as early as 2018 (Mutter, 2018). This coincides with the first widely publicised use of VP, in the TV series *The Mandalorian* (broadcast 2019-2023), of which the first series was filmed at ILM’s StageCraft volumes at Manhattan Beach Studios (Giardina, 2022; Thomas, 2025).

While we did not track individual VP projects in the same way as other XR projects, there are claims of the widespread adoption of VP led by Hollywood studios (Coherent Market Insights, 2025). Existing scholarship in this area notes that tracking VP is necessary to “help people seize the opportunities of a new way of working that might begin to address longstanding issues” (Willment & Swords, 2023, p. 17) and that the factors with the biggest effect on the adoption of VP are affordability and access to tech (Hitchen et al., 2023, p. 3).

All XR technologies

Looking at XR activity in the UK through the lens of tech adoption, and tracing which organisations and sectors have engaged with and developed use cases for these technologies, tells a story of adoption across many use cases. In the language of tech adoption, those organisations and individuals who are the slowest to adopt a new technology are dubbed the ‘laggards’. Research on laggards identifies multiple factors in speeding up tech adoption. As laggards are often smaller firms, policy interventions can help them to access newer technologies (Berlingieri et al., 2020), as can de-risking innovation as it has been found that “de-risked R&D in non-commercial contexts... is vital to maintaining growth in the sector” (Bennett et al., 2023). The CoSTAR Network provides the funding, space, expertise and opportunity to conduct R&D with XR and promote adoption of these technologies.

In this section we compare the projects identified in this report with those funded by UKRI during the same time period.

Timelines

In our previous report (Black et al., 2025), we located 529 projects starting between 2006 and 2024 that were funded by UKRI and, in this report, we located a further 380 with other funders (see Figure 10). Both sets of data show an upward trend, rising more steeply from around 2015 / 2016. From 2017, UKRI funded more projects than the other funders combined each year, except for 2022. The growth in UKRI-funded XR projects was more variable.

Figure 10. Number of XR projects funded by UKRI and other funders, 2006-2024. Selected data points are labelled for clarity.

Image courtesy of the Centre for Creative and Immersive Extended Reality (CCIXR), University of Portsmouth; photographer: Rob Hobbs.

COMPARISON WITH UKRI FUNDED XR ACTIVITY

Virtual Production Timelines

Between 2014 and 2024, there were 38 VP projects funded by UKRI; of the 41 VP studios not funded by UKRI, we have start dates for 27 of them between 2021 and 2024 (see Figure 11). UKRI awarded funding to VP-related projects before commercial VP studios started to proliferate in the UK. The earliest VP-related projects funded by UKRI were 'ASAP - A Scalable 2D/3D Architecture for Cross Media Virtual Production' in 2014 by British and Indian visual effects company Double Negative Ltd (now [DNEG](#)) and 'Real-time Interactive Cinematic Content Creation' in 2014 by film production company [Industrial Light and Magic \(UK\) Ltd](#). These projects helped to develop the technologies and pipelines necessary for virtual production. The next two projects funded by UKRI were [StoryFutures Academy: Industry Centre of Excellence in Immersive Narrative](#) in 2018, a collaboration between multiple academic, industry and arts organisations led by the National Film and Television School, and the [StoryFutures: Gateway Cluster Partnership for Audiovisual Digital Creativity](#) also in 2018, a collaboration between many academic, industry, arts and business development organisations led by Royal Holloway University of London. Many of the organisations taking part in these collaborations went on to be active in VP, such as Imaginarium, Pinewood Group Ltd, and DNEG, showing that the current provision of VP

studios, technologies and skills in the UK can be traced back to early intervention and support from UKRI.

Figure 11. Number of VP projects and studios funded by UKRI and other funders, 2014-2024.

Trends in XR Projects

For the UKRI-funded projects, we tracked the mentions of several trending topics: artificial intelligence, ED&I (equality, diversity & inclusion), heritage, and sustainability. We did the same for the XR projects funded by other funders and the VP studios (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Trends in UKRI-funded projects, projects with other funders and VP studios, 2006-2024.

Of the 529 UKRI-funded projects, 73 mentioned AI (14% of projects), 119 mentioned ED&I (22%), 150 mentioned heritage (28%), and 62 mentioned sustainability (12%). The strong presence of mentions of ED&I potentially indicates that this is expected in an application for funding from UKRI. The strong presence of heritage warrants further investigation into the relationships between heritage projects and organisations, new technologies and funders.

Of the 380 XR projects, none mentioned AI, 5 mentioned ED&I (1%), 102 mentioned heritage (27%), and 17 mentioned sustainability (4%). The low instances of mentions of AI, sustainability and ED&I are perhaps reflective of the sparsity of data about the projects. The strong presence of mentions of heritage is again indicative of active relationships between the heritage sector and new technologies.

Of the 41 VP studios, none mentioned AI or heritage, 5 mentioned ED&I (12%) and 17 mentioned sustainability (41%). This reflects a desire

by the VP studios to show that sustainability is a priority for them. It is likely that many of the studios do use AI in some capacity, and further investigation into this would be useful, as the relationship between creative practitioners and the recent availability of generative AI in particular is constantly evolving. We predict that, if our structured search strategy was used to update the data set in 2026, there would be more mentions of AI.

Locations

Comparing all the XR projects funded by UKRI and those funded by others, shows differences in the locations of those projects (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Locations of XR projects funded by UKRI and those funded by others, 2006 -2024 and VP studios active in 2025. The dots on the map represent the locations of projects and VP studios, the size of the dots represents the number of projects and studios in each location, and the colour of the dots represent whether the item being mapped is a project funded by UKRI, a project with another funder, or a VP studio. The UK's four capital cities have been labelled for reference.

The sites of UKRI-funded XR projects (gold dots, 529 projects) show a concentration in London (29%) with other projects distributed throughout

England and more sparsely in Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales.

The sites of XR projects with other funders (green dots, 380 projects) show a smaller concentration in London (15%) with other projects distributed in different locations throughout England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. When compared with the UKRI-funded projects, there is a similar concentration of projects in England, fewer in Northern Ireland, and more in Scotland and Wales.

The UKRI-funded projects took place at 142 unique locations and projects with other funders took place at 106 unique locations. Only 35 locations were the sites of both UKRI-funded projects and projects with other funders, indicating that the geographical spread of each set of projects did not overlap greatly.

While the locations of UKRI-funded XR projects indicated potential innovation deserts in more sparsely populated areas, the greater prevalence of XR projects by other funders in those locations minimises the disparity of XR activity across geographical areas of the UK.

The sites of VP studios (red dots, 41 studios) show a greater concentration in London (44%) than the XR projects with other studios predominantly located in South and Central England and to a much lesser extent in the other three nations. 31 of the 41 VP studios are located at sites that also played host to other XR projects (funded by UKRI and others). While some of these sites are major cities (Belfast, Bristol, London, Manchester, Nottingham), the others are located outside of major cities, such as Bridgend in Wales, Coatbridge in Scotland, and Windsor in England, suggesting that the occurrence of XR projects in a location made it more likely that a VP studio would be located there. There are limitations with data availability, especially when trying to locate data about events from 20 years ago. As described in the section Materials and Methods, there is no single reliable source of data about XR projects in the UK funded by bodies other than UKRI, and so the data used in this report was collected using a structured search strategy that establishes a best practice for this kind of work, but also contains many gaps. Future work looking at XR activity in the UK will be able to use and build on this methodology.

Image courtesy of [MARS Volume](#), a virtual production environment in London provided by Bild Studios.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

One of the areas of data that was not easy to locate was the specific platforms and software used in the projects. Future work on the adoption and creation of specific technologies and tools would be valuable, including a gap analysis on where further opportunities for technological development would be useful. A survey of projects, studios, and technology providers could give insights into this aspect.

Another area where more targeted analysis would be beneficial is the relationship between population density and the relevant indexes of multiple deprivation and the investment in and adoption of XR technologies, particularly with regard to the role of creative technologies in economic regeneration via the Arts. This report has re-emphasised the link between investment in XR and the heritage sector, which would benefit from further exploration. Finally, there are opportunities to look at workforce, skills, and the size and shape of the businesses delivering much of this activity, particularly in the area of virtual production. We hope our dataset provides a base from which further research may grow, in particular, user, audience, and market responses, including returns on investment, are areas that are ripe for further research.

This report, along with the Foresight Lab's previous report, has established a baseline for XR activity in the UK up until the end of 2024 and the landscape of virtual production studios in the UK as of 2025. Future work should explore the impact that the establishment of the CoSTAR Network has had in this sector.

Image courtesy of the Centre for Creative and Immersive Extended Reality (CCIXR), University of Portsmouth; photographer: Rob Hobbs .

CONCLUSIONS

This report has offered an overview of XR activity in the UK for screen, performance and digital entertainment purposes between 2006 and 2024 from funders beyond UKRI. It has also provided an overview of the active virtual production studios in the UK as of 2025. To do this, we have developed a structured search strategy to locate data about XR activity in the UK funded by charities, commercial entities, government bodies, local authorities and national arts councils. We do this to complete the picture of XR activity in the UK initiated in our previous report, [‘UK Innovation in Immersive XR Technologies for screen, performance and digital entertainment: UKRI funding trends and insights \(2006–2024\)’](#) published in May 2025, and to facilitate comparison with the work being done by the five [CoSTAR Network](#) Labs over their duration (2024–2029).

We located 380 projects and 41 VP studios. The projects took place between 2006 and 2024, with a marked increase from 2015 onwards. They mentioned multiple XR technologies, with augmented reality and virtual reality being the most common. These projects most frequently took the forms of AR trails, games, experiences, performances, apps, installations and exhibitions relating to history and local interest, followed by nature and science, and performance and storytelling. From the funding data we were able to locate (for around half of the projects), we found that the most frequent type of funder was commercial entities, followed by community development, Business Improvement Districts or Local Enterprise Partnerships, local authorities, and arts organisations, venues or events. The most frequent individual funders were National Lottery Heritage Fund, Wellcome Trust, and Arts Council England. The landscape of VP studios looks slightly different, with most currently active studios opening in 2021 or later and serving as commercial entities.

In comparing these projects with those funded by UKRI over the same time period, we found a story of tech adoption that starts with the funding of R&D projects by UKRI, bringing together academic and industry collaborators to develop XR technologies, which are then taken up by commercial entities in the establishment of VP studios. The UK is now a world leader in virtual production (Department for International Trade, 2022). This analysis, combined with our report on UKRI funding, provides the sector with baseline information regarding the maturation of the immersive technology R&D environment in the UK.

IMAGE CREDITS

cover, p.27, p.37 Julian Hughes
p.13, p.41, p.49 Rob Hobbs
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p.33, p.47 MARS Volume

DATASET

The dataset of 380 XR projects, which underpins this work, is available on the Foresight Lab Zenodo page, published with an open license. Please cite as:

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COVER IMAGE: Image courtesy of [Displace Studio](#), a mixed reality performance studio; photographer: Julian Hughes.

